

OPEN LETTER

The Blastocystis-colorectal cancer hypothesis: correlation is not causation

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Abstract

Although superficially persuasive, claims suggesting a causal link between *Blastocystis* and colorectal cancer (CRC) lack robust scientific support. As *Blastocystis* is the most common gut protist found in human populations globally, its detection in CRC patients is unsurprising and does not imply pathogenicity. Current claims championing a causal role for *Blastocystis* in CRC are based on speculative correlations, a single poorly controlled animal study, and inconsistent subtype associations. We argue that linking *Blastocystis* to CRC is premature, misleading, and may give rise to unnecessary concern in patients that are colonised by or test positive for *Blastocystis*. We emphasise the need for rigorously designed investigations to establish causal roles for any microorganism in disease and the importance of conclusions being based on solid evidence, particularly in matters of public health.

Keywords

Blastocystis, colorectal cancer, gut microbiome, correlation, causation

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As active members of the European COST (Cooperation on Science and Technology) Action *Blastocystis under One Health* (CA21105) we wish to express our concerns regarding several statements presented in the review “An Update on *Blastocystis*: Possible Mechanisms of *Blastocystis*-Mediated Colorectal Cancer” by Tocci, Das, and Sayed¹. Based on our collective expertise in *Blastocystis* research, we wish to note that no comprehensive epidemiological, *in vitro* or *in vivo* data conclusively supports the assertions of Tocci *et al.*¹ who suggest that a direct causal relationship between *Blastocystis* infection or colonisation and the development of colorectal cancer (CRC) has been established. Establishing causation requires carefully designed and integrated mechanistic and epidemiological studies with appropriate controls. As outlined, such studies currently do not exist, and the claims in the review of Tocci *et al.*¹ rely heavily on speculative interpretations of limited studies that we discuss in brief below.

Blastocystis is the most common protist in the human gut globally. More than 45 subtypes have been identified, with over 10 of these found in humans with ST3 the most prevalent globally^{2,3}. Despite the first description of *Blastocystis* being published more than 110 years ago⁴, its clinical significance is still under debate⁵⁻⁷. According to the available data, when *Blastocystis* is detected in clinical cases it is primarily associated with gastroenterological and dermatological conditions that are related to both the host’s immune status and other components of the gut microbiota⁸⁻¹¹. Although some studies have reported an increased prevalence of *Blastocystis* among cancer patients^{12,13}, these studies do not provide any evidence or mechanistic insights that would implicate a causal role for *Blastocystis* in CRC. For example, it may simply be specific changes to the local environment of the gut in CRC (including treatment-induced changes in gut ecology, immune suppression, or broader dysbiosis) could explain an increased prevalence in cancer patients in some studies. An association between *Blastocystis* and carcinogenesis has been shown in a rat model, where urinary oxidative indices correlated with carcinogenesis were shown to be higher in rats infected with *Blastocystis* than in non-infected rats¹⁴. However, to our knowledge, this is the only *in vivo* study reported in the literature and was conducted in laboratory rodents and not humans. The *Blastocystis* isolate used was ST3, the most common subtype occurring in humans, but not adapted to infect rodents, which typically harbour ST4. Most importantly, this isolate was obtained from a faecal sample of a non-symptomatic individual, concentrated on a density gradient and subsequently used to infect rats with the presence of other microbes (e.g. bacteria, viruses) in the concentrate notably not excluded. Furthermore, the morphological forms presented in the study¹⁴ appear to be inconsistent with recognised *Blastocystis* morphotypes. On this note, Tocci and colleagues¹ outline that certain *Blastocystis* subtypes are pathogenic. However, a detailed understanding of the genetic and phenotypic diversity of

Blastocystis STs and their biological significance with respect to host health and disease is limited, and robust research data linking the disease-causing potential or pathogenicity of subtypes or morphotypes to CRC is simply not available. Based on the current literature, it is not possible to differentiate *Blastocystis* subtypes and/or strains as being either commensal or pathogenic, as contradictory study findings on *Blastocystis* subtypes and pathogenicity are widespread¹⁵⁻¹⁸.

Contrary to studies suggesting a role for *Blastocystis* in CRC, a recent study using state-of-the-art metagenomic approaches that presented data from the largest cohort studied to date (involving more than 56,000 individuals from 32 countries) has demonstrated a negative correlation between CRC and *Blastocystis*¹⁹. More generally, a negative correlation between *Blastocystis* and other diseases that involve inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract e.g. ulcerative colitis and Crohn’s Disease have been reported in independent studies^{20,21}.

Conclusion

The history of microbial oncology, exemplified by *Helicobacter pylori* and gastric cancer^{22,23} demonstrates that microbial involvement in cancer is possible. However, in those cases, causation was only established after decades of carefully controlled epidemiological, mechanistic, and clinical studies. For *Blastocystis*, such a body of evidence does not currently exist, and even if we critically assess the evidence that is available, there is no credible basis for asserting that *Blastocystis* causes CRC in humans. Its high prevalence globally makes its detection in cancer patients unsurprising, and current studies provide, at best, speculative correlations. Importantly, premature claims of causation carry the risk of misleading clinicians, alarming patients, and diverting research away from more productive avenues. Furthermore, they undermine the nuanced view emerging from microbiome science²⁴⁻²⁷, where *Blastocystis* is often associated with gut health rather than disease. Whilst future research may yet clarify the potential roles of *Blastocystis*, whether neutral, beneficial, or detrimental, until such evidence exists, statements linking *Blastocystis* to cancer should be regarded as misleading and premature.

Ethics and consent statement

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Disclaimer

The views expressed in this article are those of the author(s). Publication in Open

Research does not imply endorsement by the COST ACTION funding body.

Data availability statement

No data are associated with this article.

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Sonia H Navia

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The letter addresses the controversial relationship between the gut protist *Blastocystis* and colorectal cancer (CRC). It argues that the current claim of a direct link between both conditions still lacks a solid scientific basis. The authors appropriately highlight the high persistence of *Blastocystis* in healthy populations, which makes its detection in CRC patients not entirely unexpected, but not necessarily evidence of a pathogenic role. In this sense, the manuscript offers a useful and timely counterpoint to premature causal interpretations.

The authors clearly identify the main concern: the publication of a review (Tocci et al.) that suggests mechanisms of causality without definitive evidence. They also explain well why this can be problematic, as it may unnecessarily alarm colonized patients. Importantly, the manuscript does not ignore studies that support the pathogenicity hypothesis, but instead contrasts them with evidence from large meta-analyses and calls for more rigorous mechanistic and epidemiological studies.

I do, however, have a few suggestions that could strengthen the manuscript:

- First, although CRC clearly changes the intestinal environment, the discussion could expand a bit more on how immunological, physiological, and morphological changes during cancer development may favor opportunistic colonization by *Blastocystis*. This would reinforce the idea that the association may be a consequence of the disease rather than its cause.
- Second, the authors criticize the inconsistent forms described in previous studies. This is an important point, but it would help to clarify whether this refers to problems in morphological identification, terminology, or interpretation across studies. Also, if the authors suggest that different forms may have distinct effects in the colon, that idea should be presented cautiously, since the biological relevance of several *Blastocystis* morphotypes is still debated.
- Finally, I would suggest that future studies should go beyond reporting simple PCR-based presence/absence and also include parasite burden, for example by qPCR. Given that the colon tumor microenvironment changes substantially, it is plausible that cancer may favor increased *Blastocystis* abundance without implying a causal role. In that sense, distinguishing colonization from possible overgrowth could help better frame the

association and avoid overinterpretation.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Yes

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Yes

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Cancer immunology, CRC microbiota

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

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Camelia Munteanu

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In this open letter, Kurt et al. emphasize that the implication that *Blastocystis* sp. may act as a causative factor in colorectal cancer (CRC) is not sufficiently supported by the current evidence. They present solid arguments outlining the limitations of the available studies and stress that further experimental and mechanistic research is necessary before any causal relationship can be established.

Importantly, the authors caution against prematurely assigning a pathogenic role to *Blastocystis* sp. in CRC in the absence of robust supporting data. By carefully examining the existing literature, they challenge the assumption that this organism should be regarded as a confirmed etiological factor in colorectal carcinogenesis.

Overall, this commentary is timely and relevant. It provides a balanced perspective on the topic and encourages a more cautious interpretation of the current findings. For these reasons, it is appropriate for Indexing.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Yes

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Yes

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Cancer etiology, cancer biology, biomarkers, cancer omics analysis

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.
